

PECULIARITIES OF CLINICAL COURSE OF FOOD ALLERGY IN YOUNG CHILDREN

¹Tukhtaeva Olmakhon Tashevna, ²Nazarov Azadbek Ahmedovich

¹associate professor, Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, ²professor, Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14186059>

Abstract. *The development of food allergy in children has led to a significant increase in adverse reactions associated with food consumption. Food allergy, being the first sensitization by time of development, plays a huge role in the formation and subsequent development of all allergic diseases in children. The study of immunologic aspects of food allergy will be important for the primary prevention of food allergy. In the postnatal period, children belonging to this risk group should be identified and preventive dietary therapy should be carried out with the exclusion of highly allergenic foods.*

Keywords: *food allergy, cow's milk proteins, infants, immunity.*

Annotatsiya. *Bolalarda oziq-ovqat allergiyasining rivojlanishi oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini iste'mol qilish bilan bog'liq salbiy reaksiyalarning sezilarli darajada oshishiga olib keldi. Oziq-ovqat allergiyasi rivojlanish nuqtai nazaridan birinchi sensibilizatsiya bo'lib, bolalarda barcha allergik kasalliklarning shakllanishi va keyingi rivojlanishida katta rol o'ynaydi. Oziq-ovqat allergiyasining immunologik jihatlari bo'yicha tadqiqotlar oziq-ovqat allergiyasining birlamchi profilaktikasini amalga oshirish uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'ladi. Postnatal davrda ushbu xavf guruhiga mansub bolalarni aniqlash va yuqori alergik oziq-ovqatlarni istisno qilgan holda profilaktik parhez terapiyasini o'tkazish lozim.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ovqat allergiyasi, sigir suti oqsili, erta yoshli bolalar, immunitet.*

Аннотация. *Развития пищевой аллергии у детей привело к существенному росту нежелательных реакций, связанных с употреблением продуктов питания. Пищевая аллергия являясь первой по времени развития сенсibilизацией играет огромную роль в формировании и последующим развитием всех аллергических заболеваний у детей. Исследование иммунологических аспектов пищевой аллергии будет иметь важное значение для осуществления первичной профилактики пищевой аллергии. В постнатальном периоде необходимо выявить детей принадлежащих к этой группе риска, и провести превентивную диетотерапию с исключением высокоаллергенных продуктов.*

Ключевые слова: *пищевая аллергия, белки коровьего молока, дети раннего возраста, иммунитет.*

Relevance. Food allergy in children can develop due to improper nutrition of the mother during pregnancy or breastfeeding. The main cause of the disease is a genetic disorder of the immune system, which can also be hereditary in nature. Food allergies in children are usually caused by the following factors: Failure to breastfeed the child, feeding artificial formula containing different proteins from cow's or goat's milk; Premature birth Diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, biliary tract or liver.

Food intolerance and food allergy have grown into a global medical and social problem in recent decades. The development of food allergy in children is multifactorial. Risk factors for food allergy in children include allergic diseases in the mother, toxicosis of pregnant women, drug therapy of pregnant women, overloading the diet of lactating women with dairy products. It is known that among children of the first year of life, allergy to cow's milk proteins is more

common in children who are artificially fed (2-7%). Unreasonably early introduction of various milk mixtures, including non-adapted ones, as well as premature (2-3 months and earlier) administration of milk porridge, especially to children genetically predisposed to atopy, contributes to the development of milk allergy in them. The widespread food intolerance and food allergy to agents and antimicrobial agents in industry and in the home, the sharp deterioration of the environment, the uncontrolled use of antibiotics, resulting in changes in the normal microbiocenosis, etc. [1,2,5,12].

It is estimated that there are approximately 250-520 million people worldwide with food allergies [2,3,4,5,7]. Today, more than 170 food products are considered potential allergens, but the list of priority food allergens varies depending on the geographical region of residence and dietary traditions of the population [8,9,10,11].

In the children we examined, an important role is played by 1-allergic diathesis, 2-artificial feeding, 3- genetic factors, 4- maternal toxicosis during pregnancy. Polysensitization and sensitization of the body are not uncommon. There were also symptoms such as headache, weakness, insomnia, nausea and diarrhea [6,12].

Aim of the study. To study clinical manifestations and sensitization in young children, to various allergens, peculiarities of nutrition of sick children with allergic diseases using modern methods of in vitro allergodiagnosics.

Materials and methods of the study. We examined 120 infants aged from 6 months to 3 years. The research was conducted in 2 stages. The first stage: questionnaire and survey, in which the data were collected by interviewing the parents of children; the second stage - clinical and laboratory examination in the hospital. Food allergens characteristic for our country were included in the modified allergen panels.

In general, the group of patients with IgE-mediated food allergy consisted of 116 children (girls - 76.8%, boys - 23.2%), 4 children were found to have pseudoallergic reactions.

In the development of allergic reactions in children food products of plant origin are of great importance. Proteins of cereal grains, primarily wheat, less frequently rice, oats, buckwheat, have a pronounced allergenic activity. Soy products may be the cause of atopic dermatitis and gastrointestinal manifestations of allergy in young children.

Immunologic examination included the following studies. Determination of total and specific IgE serum concentration by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay on ELISA kits - total IgE.

Results and Discussion. The survey revealed that an aggravated family history in one or more of the closest relatives (sibs, mother, father) for allergic diseases increased in 87.9% of children. Atopic diseases in one of the closest relatives was found in 66 children (55%), in 46 children (38.3%), in 8 children (6.7%) allergic diseases were not found in the allergic anamnesis in relatives and parents.

Antibiotics in the neonatal period were given to 47% of children; clinically significant gastrointestinal disorders were noted in 32% of children.

The results of allergoanamnesis showed that 45% of mothers of the examined children during pregnancy and 47% of mothers during breastfeeding consumed dairy products in the amount of up to 1.5 liters per day, which is 2 times higher than the normative values for healthy pregnant women in the second half of pregnancy. Clinical symptoms in 44.6% of cases manifested as oral allergic syndrome, GI symptoms in 51%, respiratory symptoms in 36.6% and skin manifestations in 29.3% of cases. The time of manifestation of the first symptoms after consumption of the “guilty” food allergen was 21.2+ 13.9 minutes.

According to the clinical questionnaire of the mothers of the examined children, 25% of patients had sensitization to only one food allergen, and 75% of children indicated more than one product - the trigger of allergic reactions. Children with multivalent sensitization had significantly earlier onset of PA compared to patients sensitized to a single food product.

The spectrum of allergens to which allergen specific IgE in serum was detected was as follows. Gastrointestinal disorders were noted in 60.4% of patients after ingestion of milk, egg 35.7%, apple 35.3%, tomato 15%, peach 12.1%, peanut 8%, carrot 7.4%. Respiratory disorders were manifested as follows: to milk 25.7%, eggs 25.5%, carrot 15.3%, tomato 15.2%, peach 8.6%, peanut 8.4%, apple 5.7%.

Skin changes were accompanied by intake of milk in 42.7%, egg 35.1%, tomato 18.8%, peanut 15.2%, peach 8.6%, carrot 8.4% apple 5.1%, cases. In the above groups, there was an increase in serum IgE above 5.5 IU/mL.

Conclusion. According to the results of our research we can conclude: Food hypersensitivity according to the questionnaire-questionnaire method was detected in 39% of children aged 6 months to 3 years living in Tashkent. Among them 9.7% of children have milk intolerance, probably related to true allergy to cow's milk proteins. According to the data of specific diagnostics in children with food hypersensitivity, food sensitization to cow's milk protein 43.1% and to chicken egg protein 31% was most often revealed.

Also, studies have shown that modern trends in the development of PA in children have led to a significant increase in the prevalence of adverse reactions associated with food consumption. PA, being the first sensitization by time of development, plays a huge role in the formation and subsequent development of all allergic diseases in children.

The study of immunologic aspects of food allergy will be important for the development of new approaches to the diagnosis and prevention of food allergy. For the primary prevention of food allergy in the postnatal period, it is necessary to identify children at risk of development and conduct preventive dietary therapy with the exclusion of highly allergenic foods.

REFERENCES

1. Allergology (Federal Clinical Recommendations) edited by Acad. R.M. Khaitov. Moscow. 2014; 106-109.
2. Balabolkin I.I. Food allergy in children // Allergology and Immunology in Pediatrics, 2008. - № 4 (15). - C. 7-15.
3. I.N. Zakharova, I.V. Berezhnaya FGBOU DPO “Russian Medical Academy of Continuing Professional Education” of the Ministry of Health of Russia, Moscow. “Food allergy in children: what is its growth associated with?”. 10.21518/2079-701X-2018-17-156-162.
4. Namazova-Baranova L.S. Allergy in children: from theory to practice. M: Union of Pediatricians of Russia, 2010; 166-199.
5. Nazarov. O.A., Tukhtaeva O.T. Influence of sublingual specific immunotherapy on the dynamics of sensitization indices in pollen bronchial asthma. Pediatrics. T. 2023; 4: 103-106.
6. Nazarov. O.A., Tukhtaeva O.T. Oral allergic syndrome in children as a cross-reactivity phenomenon. Pediatrics. 2019; 3: 73-77.
7. Evdokimova TA Ogorodova LM, et al. Clinical manifestations of IgE mediated food allergy in children. Pediatrics. 2014. Vol. 93. no. 3; 20-21. Lopez CM, Yarrarapu SNS, Mendez MD.: Food Allergies. 2023 Jul 24. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan-. PMID: 29489188

8. Lopez CM, Yarrarapu SNS, Mendez MD, Knizel JE. Food Allergies (Nursing). 2023 Jul 24. In: Stat Pearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan-. PMID: 34033312.
9. Kolb L, Ferrer-Bruker SJ. Atopic Dermatitis. 2023 Aug 8. In: StatPearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan-. PMID: 28846349.
10. Kelleher MM, Phillips R, Brown SJ, Cro S, Cornelius V, Carlsen KCL, Skjerven HO, Rehbindler EM, Lowe AJ, Dissanayake E, Shimojo N, Yonezawa K, Ohya Y, Yamamoto-Hanada K, Morita K, Axon E, Cork M, Cooke A, Van Vogt E, Schmitt J, Weidinger S, McClanahan D, Simpson E, Duley L, Askie LM, Williams HC, Boyle RJ. [Skin care interventions in infants for preventing eczema and food allergy](#). *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2022 Nov 14;11(11):CD013534. doi:10.1002/14651858.CD013534.pub3. PMID: 36373988
11. “Risk factors for severe reactions in food allergy: Rapid evidence review with meta-analysis” Paul J Turner 1, Stefania Arasi 2, Barbara Ballmer-Weber 3 4, Alessia Baseggio Conrado 1, Antoine Deschildre 5, Jennifer Gerdtts 6, Susanne Halcken 7, Antonella Muraro 8, Nandinee Patel 1, Ronald Van Ree 9, Debra de Silva 10, Margitta Worm 11, Torsten Zuberbier 11, Graham Roberts 12 13; Global Allergy, Asthma European Network (GA2LEN) Food Allergy Guideline Group. 2022 Sep;77(9):2634-2652. doi: 10.1111/all.15318. Epub 2022 Apr 28.
12. Tukhtaeva O.T. Risk of development and chronology of allergic diseases in children. *Pediatrics*. 2019; 1: 60-65.